

Labor Activity Prediction Using Machine Learning

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Abstract— In the realm of ubiquitous computing and context aware computing, labour activity detection is a hot issue. In this research, we present a labour activity detection approach in which accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer data from wearable devices are gathered and utilised as input to a random forests (RF) model to categorise labour activity. The random forests model for labour activity recognition is constructed, as well as the algorithm, which is built and assessed. Experiment results validated our technique, which reached an overall accuracy of around 99.9%.

Keywords—Construction Management, Machine Learning, Activity Recognition, Labor.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the field of artificial intelligence and ubiquitous computing, labour activity recognition is a hotspot. The technique of data collection divides labour activity recognition into two categories: labour activity recognition based on computer vision and labour activity recognition based on wearable devices. Activity detection based on wearable sensors has grown in popularity because it may be performed without regard to time, location, or other constraints. When a human moves, a labour activity detection approach based on wearable devices collects environmental and physiological characteristics by placing several sensors on different sections of the body. After a sequence of processing and analysis, this data may be utilised to assess the human body's movement state.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

- A. The HAR model is a demanding and expanding topic of ML research that utilises sensor and computer vision systems (jobanputra et al,2019). HAR models have traditionally depended on sensor-based systems, but the fast advancement of computer vision (CV) and deep learning (DL) has resulted in complex algorithms with improved accuracy.
- B. B.Pirttikangas et al. (2006) examined a model that employed various multilayer perceptron and k-nearest neighbour (K-NN) algorithms to identify activity, achieving an overall accuracy of 90.61 percent. This study has an overall accuracy of 90 percent. Several years later, Ahmed and Loutfi (2013) used case-based reasoning support vector

machine (SVMS) and neural network (NN) to obtain an overall accuracy of 0.86, 0.62, and 0.59 for their unique activity (breathing, walking, running or sitting) Wang et al. (2013) described a wearable system that used passive tags and attained an accuracy of 93.6 percent.

III. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this research is to assess the actions of construction workers. In this way, the artificial intelligence model created to forecast a construction worker's behaviours is implemented step by step, as indicated in the flowchart below: -

Labor activity prediction methodology.

The steps that required to be followed are:

1. Data Collection
2. Data Pre-processing
3. Model Building
4. Analyzing

5. Result

A.Data Collection: There are 8 rows and 46 columns in dataset.

B. Data Pre-processing: This is the first stage in every machine learning process. This procedure comprises data cleansing, transformation, and reduction. All of this is done to improve the effectiveness of the data. The data may be analysed to improve the accuracy of our model. As a result, the categorization will be right.

1. Cleaning Data – Initially, the data is cleansed. This is where people remove undesirable entries. The noisy data can be eliminated from the dataset as well.

2. Splitting of Data – After cleaning the data, it is divided into training and testing datasets. Following that, the data selected for training is utilised to train our model.

C. Machine Learning: In the construction industry, a machine learning algorithm is utilised to anticipate worker activities. The accuracy of a classifier is determined by how it is taught. Many classifiers are used to forecast labour activity. The accuracy of the classifier is determined by how it is taught. A classifier should have a high level of accuracy.

1.Random Forest Classifier: To forecast labour activity, the Random Forest Classification method is employed. This algorithm belongs to the category of machine learning algorithms. Random Forest is a classifier that uses a number of decision trees on different subsets of a given dataset and averages them to enhance the predicted accuracy of that dataset. The bigger the number of trees in the forest, the higher the accuracy and the lower the risk of overfitting.

IV. BUILD MODEL

The fundamental phase in labour activity recognition is model construction. When creating the model, the user use algebra. The steps are as follows: MODEL

1. Import the packages that are necessary.

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings('ignore')
%matplotlib inline
```

2. Load Dataset.

```
df1=pd.read_csv('HAR_Dataset/Sensor_acc.csv')
df2=pd.read_csv('HAR_Dataset/Sensor_gyro.csv')
df3=pd.read_csv('HAR_Dataset/Sensor_magneto.csv')
```

```
df1[df1['activity']=='Vibrating']['acc_x_axis'][0:500].plot()
```



```
df1[df1['activity']=='Vibrating']['acc_y_axis'][0:500].plot()
```

[4]: <matplotlib.axes._subplots.AxesSubplot at 0x1eb0b18828>


```
df1[df1['activity']=='Vibrating']['acc_z_axis'][0:500].plot()
```


4. 3-axis Gyroscope data from vibrating activity.

```
[6]: df2[df2['activity']=='Vibrating']['gyro_x_axis'][0:500].plot()
```

[6]: <matplotlib.axes._subplots.AxesSubplot at 0x1eacd12e8>


```
[7]: df2[df2['activity']=='Vibrating']['gyro_y_axis'][0:500].plot()
```

[7]: <matplotlib.axes._subplots.AxesSubplot at 0x1eace09128>


```
: df2[df2['activity']=='Vibrating']['gyro_z_axis'][0:500].plot()
```

: <matplotlib.axes._subplots.AxesSubplot at 0x1eace6e5c0>

5. 3-axis Magnetometer data from vibrating activity.

```
[9]: df3[df3['activity']=='Vibrating']['magn_x_axis'][0:500].plot()
```

[9]: <matplotlib.axes._subplots.AxesSubplot at 0x1eaced0ba8>


```
df3[df3['activity']=='Vibrating']['magn_y_axis'][0:500].plot()
```

<matplotlib.axes._subplots.AxesSubplot at 0xe5386a9240>


```
df3[df3['activity']=='Vibrating']['magn_z_axis'][0:500].plot()
```

<matplotlib.axes._subplots.AxesSubplot at 0xe5386b2588>

6.Feature Extraction after windowing.

- **Mean:** Calculates the mean the seperated windows values
- **Variance:** Calculates the variance the seperated windows values
- **Median:** Calculates the median the seperated windows values
- **Maximum:** Calculates the maximum value the seperated windows values
- **Minimum:** Calculates the minimum value the seperated windows values
- **Sum values:** Calculates the sum over the seperated windows values
- **Length:** Calculates the length the seperated windows values
- **Standard deviation:** Calculates the standard deviation the seperated windows values
- **Root mean score:** Calculates the quadratic mean the seperated windows values

```
df=pd.read_csv('HAR_Dataset/Sensors_features.csv')
```

7. Dataset Details.

- **17 Columns**
- **timestamp:** Time Details
- **activity:** Labour Activity

3 sensors x,y,z

- **mean:** Calculates the mean the seperated windows values
- **variance:** Calculates the variance the seperated windows values
- **median:** Calculates the median the seperated windows values
- **maximum:** Calculates the maximum value the seperated windows values
- **minimum:** Calculates the minimum value the seperated windows values

8. Data Cleaning

```
df.isnull().sum()

timestamp      0
acc_xs_mean    0
acc_ys_mean    0
acc_zs_mean    0
acc_xs_var     0
acc_ys_var     0
acc_zs_var     0
acc_xs_mad     0
acc_ys_mad     0
acc_zs_mad     0
acc_xs_max     0
```

9.Data Visualization

10.Machine Learning Algorithm

Random Forest Classification.

```
# Create Model
clf = RandomForestClassifier(n_estimators=50, random_state=42)

# Train the Model
clf.fit(X_train, y_train)

RandomForestClassifier(bootstrap=True, class_weight=None, criterion='gini',
    max_depth=None, max_features='auto', max_leaf_nodes=None,
    min_impurity_decrease=0.0, min_impurity_split=None,
    min_samples_leaf=1, min_samples_split=2,
    min_weight_fraction_leaf=0.0, n_estimators=50, n_jobs=1,
    oob_score=False, random_state=42, verbose=0, warm_start=False)

# Predict the Test set Result
y_pred = clf.predict(X_test)
y_pred

array([3, 2, 2, ..., 3, 2, 0], dtype=int64)
```

V. RESULT

Accuracy Score

```
from sklearn import metrics
print('Accuracy Score:', round(metrics.accuracy_score(y_test,y_pred)*100,2),'%')

Accuracy Score: 99.8 %
```

Confusion Matrix

```
c_matrix=metrics.confusion_matrix(y_test, y_pred)
c_matrix

array([[12081, 5, 5, 0],
       [ 13, 11993, 5, 0],
       [ 57, 6, 11934, 0],
       [ 4, 1, 1, 11895]], dtype=int64)
```


VI. CONCLUSION

In this case study, we demonstrated how machine learning may assist in the analysis of sensor data. We can identify activities, categorise or group participants to activities, and get further insights about activity durations and patterns of individuals engaging in those activities. The study looked various approaches to labour activity detection and outlined the entire data collection technique for HAR, as well as the Python-based machine learning-based data analysis process. The random forest approach outperformed the other machine learning algorithms employed by 99.8 percent.

REFERENCES

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